

Interpersonal Relationships and Well-being: A Systematic Review of Empirical Evidence

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All individuals have experienced the moments when presence and interactions with others become burdensome and overwhelming- perhaps during a conflicting or opinionated conversation with family members, friends or colleagues, resulting in a dramatic tension. Jean-Paul Sartre, an existentialist philosopher has put this sentiment in his famous phrase from his 1944 play No Exit: "Hell is other people." The play depicts three characters living in a room with a realization that they are not tormented by any sort of physical pain but from the constant judgmental attitude, blame games and constant scrutiny of each other. This iconic line in his play illustrates how human interpersonal relationships can strip away the freedom, autonomy and authenticity. The objectification of self by the look of others and the way they only see shortcomings creates an incongruence between self-perception and how others define us. This idea, where the presence of others becomes a source of mental and existential anguish rather than comfort, is in sharp contrast to one of the longest studies on happiness in modern psychology, whose findings state that positive interpersonal relationships are the cornerstone of a fulfilling and happy life. This systematic literature review seeks to explore this philosophical pessimism with empirical optimism and understanding mediating and moderating factors of how interpersonal relationships influence happiness and challenging the notion that Sartre acknowledged as inevitably 'hell'.

Keywords: Interpersonal relationship, happiness, and well-being

Interpersonal relationships are reciprocation of emotional and social interactions between an individual and the relationship system. The family, friends, romantic or sexual partners, or even community groups that involve support, emotional exchanges, and interactions that can range from casual to deeply intimate and the life is lived in these relationship systems and the quality of life depends on the outcome of the interaction of the individual with the relationship systems (APA, 2018). Relationship scholars have described interpersonal relationships as the interplay of interactions of the person with significant others and it is not just casual chats. These interactions shape emotions, cognition and behavior, giving us a sense of relatedness and belonging. The need for belonging (Baumeister & Leary, 1995). Interpersonal relationships means social and emotional connections and interactions of significance among two or more individuals which includes family bonds, social relationships like friendships, romantic/sexual partnerships, community ties like neighbourhood and religious groups and connections at workplace, that involves elements like reciprocity, communication, trust and support (Berscheid, 1994). In psychological terms, such relationships are not merely transactional but shape our behaviors, emotions, and overall sense of belonging. Attachment negotiation, connect and separation, power, maintenance of balance and unconscious fear are related concepts to human relations. Human life is dependent on relationships since

conception; it depends on the mother which in turn depends on family and significant others at the time of pregnancy. From an evolutionary perspective, humans also need to stay in groups and form relationships in order to avoid injury, get food, reproduce and rear the young.

The conceptualization of happiness in terms of subjective well-being (SWB), a concept that explains the relative nature of happiness, how people evaluate their lives and how life is and how life should be, is also known as contentment. It also includes life satisfaction and affective components like positive emotions and low negative emotions (Diener, 1984; Diener et al., 1999). The paradigm of happiness theories has shifted the nature of happiness from transient moments of positive emotions to authenticity, inner peace, contentment and flourishing (Lyubomirsky, 2007; Layous & Lyubomirsky, 2014).

What is the relevance of this topic now? The rapidly changing structure of society, urbanization, dual employment and shift in family structure, from joint families to only nuclear ones, but rather unconventional, which is decreasing social and community support, hence resulting in a loneliness epidemic (Chadda & Deb, 2013). Ipsos (2021) survey figured that 43% of urban youth Indians feel lonely, with 18% in metropolitan cities like Mumbai reporting constant isolation (Loneliness in India, 2021). This loneliness and not having interpersonal relationships not only deprives them of personal joy; it also spikes healthcare costs and lowers productivity at the workplace, making it an issue that can't be ignored (Holt-Lunstad et al., 2015). There are cultural differences in the conceptualization of happiness. India, country with eastern collectivist values where community and interpersonal relationship as considered as extensions of self and the belief in saying "Ek akela thak jaata hai" that one alone will get tired, this disconnect feels like an alienation to the cultural roots.

Sartre's view, is thought-provoking and may benefit many

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situations, but it is not holistic, as it is missing the sunnier side of having interpersonal relationships. The idea of “hell is other people” is based on the interaction with people who limit the freedom of other individuals, objectify and criticize others in order to feel good about themselves (Stawell, 2021). The recent scientific evidence, however, claims that quality relationships can actually boost psychological needs fulfillment and well-being (Wilson, 1967; Kemper, 1991). The supportive relations act as a buffer against stress, enhance resilience and positive emotions that are core components of SWB (Cohen & Wills, 1985; Holt-Lunstad et al., 2010). The modern psychology with its empirically investigated evidence challenges Sartre's philosophical existential lens and poses a critical evaluation of whether other people can be hell, and whether there is a possibility they can also be heaven? The scientific evidence inclines toward yes, on conditions of the quality of relationships, trust and mutual support in the relationships.

Rationale of the Study

There is a large body of research supporting that supportive, fulfilling, and good relationships keep us healthy and happy and loneliness makes us sick (Waldinger & Schulz, 2023; Diener & Seligman, 2002; Lyubomirsky & Lepper, 1999). There are theoretical standpoint that interpersonal relationships are foundational frameworks, such as Attachment (Mikulincer & Shaver, 2019) and Self-Determination Theory (Ryan & Deci, 2000), explaining the plausible connections between interpersonal relationship and well-being. The rationale for this review is to understand the applied and theoretical dimensions of the association of interpersonal relationships and subjective well-being/ happiness. The evidence from science also claims that individuals with positive social support have higher levels of resilience, positive emotions and life satisfaction and loneliness, negative emotions are associated with dysfunctional and poor quality relationships (Umberson & Karas Montez, 2010). The present review is an attempt to analyze and synthesize consistent findings and identifications of outcomes in various contexts, like individualistic and collectivist societies (Kwan et al., 1997).

The recent researches in digital milieu and new forms of communication in the form of online social networks adds more dimension to interpersonal relationships, highlighting and understanding the role of and quality of online connections on demoting or promoting levels of happiness. The applied implications of this review would help us to comprehensively understand the impact of interpersonal relationships on well being and happiness, which can further guide to develop intervention plan and program meant to enhance mental well-being. Such programs can be developed for individuals as well as the community in order to cultivate relationship and social skills, strengthen existing and developing social support systems and enhance emotional intelligence so that positive emotions can flourish and psychological distress can be prevented. This review would also focus on the gaps in existing literature like effect of ambivalent or toxic connections, workplace relationships and challenges in interpersonal connections of marginalized populations. Overall, reviewing literature on interpersonal relationships and happiness is crucial for theory advancement

Taken together, examining studies on interpersonal relationships and happiness is essential for advancing theory, informing practice, and developing a holistic understanding of well-being as a socially

embedded phenomenon.

Research Questions

This review process seeks to answer the research question: “What is the association between interpersonal relationships and happiness, and what factors mediate or moderate this link?”

Based on the research question, the following twofold objectives were formulated:

- To analyze empirical evidence from qualitative and quantitative research to map the strength, nature, and direction of this interpersonal relationship and well being.
- To identify gaps in the literature, such as Eastern and Western contexts, the role of online connections, and effective interventions to reduce loneliness.

The integration of knowledge of philosophy and science, the review investigates nurturing strong positive connections, which can counter Sartre's gloomy outlook, offering practical insights for policymakers, mental health practitioners and educators. Community is the asset that must be utilized by Eastern cultures and initiatives like mental health campaigns and local support groups can help rebuild social ties. The study seeks the transformation of the “hell” of interpersonal relationships into a heaven of joy, fostering well-being and together a - happier society.

Method

This systematic literature review was done with the help of Google Scholar. Eligible studies were peer-reviewed, English-language, empirical research on adults (18+) examining direct links between interpersonal relationships (family, friends, partners, communities) and happiness (subjective well-being, including life satisfaction & affect). Quantitative, qualitative, or mixed-methods designs were included. Exclusions included non-empirical works, non-human or pediatric studies, and research not directly linking relationships to happiness. Searches Google Scholar from January 2000 to August 2020, supplemented by hand-searching reference lists of key reviews (Holt-Lunstad et al., 2010). Search terms included (“interpersonal relationships” OR “social relationships” OR “friendships”) AND (“happiness” OR “subjective well-being” OR “life satisfaction”). The titles/abstracts and full texts were reviewed. A narrative synthesis integrated the quantitative and qualitative findings, with tables summarizing study characteristics.

Results

This systematic literature review synthesized 32 studies from 2000 to 2020, including meta-analyses and systematic reviews, examining the association between interpersonal relationships and happiness (subjective well-being). Table 1 summarizes key findings by theme. Social relationships strongly predicted well-being, with a meta-analysis of 148 studies ($N = 308,849$) showing a 50% increased survival odds ($OR = 1.50$) and correlations with life satisfaction ($r = 0.13-0.20$), emphasizing quality over quantity (Holt-Lunstad et al., 2010; Pinquart & Sörensen, 2000). Healthy romantic relationships boosted happiness via support ($r = 0.20-0.40$), while poor-quality ties reduced well-being, per a meta-analysis of 93 studies (Proulx et al., 2007). Friendships lowered depression and enhanced life satisfaction, with a review of 25 studies noting moderate effects ($r = 0.20-0.30$) (Demir & Weitekamp, 2007). Loneliness mediated negative effects on

happiness ($r = -0.25$), as shown in a 2020 meta-analysis ($N = 75,000$) (Buecker et al., 2020). Interventions fostering social engagement yielded small effects ($d = 0.15-0.25$) across 50 studies (Okun et al., 2013). Research indicated Eastern cultures showed stronger

relational ties in their collectivist societies ($r = 0.15-0.35$) (Braithwaite & Holt-Lunstad, 2016). Trust, care and empathy play a critical role in maintaining positive relationships.

Table 1

Summary of Key Findings on Interpersonal Relationships and Happiness (2000-2020)

Theme	Key Studies/Reviews	Summary of Findings	Sample Size/Scope	Effect Size/Strength
General Association	Holt-Lunstad et al. (2010); Pinqart & Sørensen (2000)	Strong social ties increase survival and life satisfaction; quality over quantity.	148 studies (N = 308,849); 287 studies (older adults).	OR = 1.50; $r = 0.13-0.20$
Romantic Relationships	Proulx et al. (2007)	Healthy romantic relationships boost happiness; poor-quality relationships lower well-being.	93 studies	$r = 0.20-0.40$
Friendships	Demir & Weitekamp (2007)	Friendships reduce depression and enhance satisfaction.	25 studies	$r = 0.20-0.30$
Mediators/ Moderators	Buecker et al. (2020)	Loneliness mediates negative effects on happiness.	75,000 participants	$r = -0.25$
Interventions	Okun et al. (2013)	Social engagement interventions improve happiness.	50 studies	$d = 0.15-0.25$
Cultural Factors	Braithwaite & Holt-Lunstad (2016)	Family ties are stronger in collectivist societies.	Narrative review	$r = 0.15-0.35$

Discussion

The existing literature from 2000 to 2020 reported the multifaceted and significant association between interpersonal relationships and subjective well-being/ happiness, advocating for the fact of a paradigmatic shift in theories of well-being/ happiness. In consistency with scientific evidence, high quality and positive social connections including family members, neighbours, friends, romantic/ sexual partners and colleagues emerged as significant determinants of positive affect and life satisfaction (Holt-Lunstad et al., 2010). Individuals with strong friendship bonds reported high perceived social support and friends act as a buffer in tough times, highlighting their role in enhancing longevity and resilience (Demir & Weitekamp, 2007). Romantic relationships work in two ways; positive romantic relations contribute to well being via affection and emotional support, and yet they can detract if there are conflicts and tension in romantic relationships (Proulx et al., 2007).

Loneliness acts as a mediator and can intensify the psychological distress and other negative outcomes, whereas moderators such as trust and care can amplify well-being, hence advocating for psychosocial models that focus on the dynamic relations rather than static traits (Buecker et al., 2020). The review also suggests actionable ways for enhancing well-being by developing and maintaining interventions, including positive social engagement, networking by including in kindness acts (seva karya) and volunteering, resulting in small but significant improvement in well-being (Okun et al., 2013). This review also places greater importance on family bonds, which have a strong correlation with well-being, taking into account cultural nuances and focusing on the role of social structure in enhancing well being in collectivist societies (Braithwaite & Holt-Lunstad, 2016).

The findings of reviews reverberate with the theoretical

frameworks focusing on the dependency on others, attachment or need to belong hypothesis, hence stating that interpersonal relationships are essential for human thriving (Baumeister & Leary, 1995) and contradicting Sartre's cynicism of "Hell are other people" (Stawell, 2021).

Besides all the insights sought from the review, certain limitations demand consideration such as timeline frame of the review from 2000 to 2020, which may be overlook some emerging trends, such as the effect of online relations post COVID-19 and the prevalence of studies that were conducted on a Western sample, so its generalization to diverse culture sample is questionable. There was heterogeneity in the methodology of studies reviewed making it difficult to identify causal influences that can inflate positive associations.

Implications for Practice and Policy

The review offers evidence for implications for counsellors and clinical psychologists where relationship-based interventions and social connections like family and friend circles can be utilized in therapy to alleviate loneliness and augment well being, especially among marginalized populations. Another significant implication of this review is in clinical practice, mental health policy, and community programs and initiatives for the positive development and well being of community. Based on friendship research, the review suggests for developing programs in educational settings, where happiness among students can be enhanced (Demir & Weitekamp, 2007). At workplace, policies for promotion of team-building can decrease stress and boost efficiency, taking the cushioning effect of social support into account (Cohen & Wills, 1985). Overall, the review highlights the integration of interpersonal factors into broader health strategies by taking account of relational dynamics.

Suggestions for Future Research

The future studies in this area should address the identified gaps. The time span of review can be extended beyond the years 2000 to 2020 literature to assimilate post-COVID data, investigating how virtual platforms are mediating the relationships and happiness in eastern contexts like India (Loades et al., 2020). Reviews taking account of longitudinal designs with varied samples, including more culturally diverse, marginalized groups are needed to demonstrate cause and effect and for in depth exploration of cultural moderators (Braithwaite & Holt-Lunstad, 2016). For comprehending the nuanced dynamics, the qualitative explorations of the subjective experiences among eastern collectivist societies are required, and advanced statistical approaches incorporated with meta-analyses for example network analysis for identification of relational patterns, could reduce biases and rectify effect size estimates (Borenstein et al., 2009).

Conclusion

To conclude, this review provides affirmation that high-quality, strong positive interpersonal relationships are the bedrock of well-being and happiness, offering protection against adversity through emotional resilience and enhancing life satisfaction. The challenges like cultural variations, psychological distress and loneliness persist but there is While challenges like loneliness and cultural variations persist, strategic interventions and targeted actions can bring meaningful and constructive change. The emphasis on relational health in policies and in practice can promote greater well-being in society, by metamorphosing the "hell" into "harmony". The researchers in the future must consider the gaps and make further advances in order to maintain this impetus, eventually leading the way to connected, contended, and fulfilled lives.

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Received February 13, 2026

Revision received March 2, 2026

Accepted March 6, 2026